

Data on the Draft Genome Sequence of *Bacillus* sp. Strain AN2 Isolated from Agricultural Soil in Brazil

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. Authors ICND and AMC designed the study and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Authors AS, JBS, JVRF, LCB, VRF, JJVC and RMA managed the analyses of the study. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Data Article

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ABSTRACT

Aims: This research aims to report the genome sequence of the *Bacillus* sp. strain AN2, isolated from agricultural soil from Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

Place and Duration of Study: Laboratory of Environmental Biotechnology, Western Rio Janeiro State University in Brazil, between January 2019 and December 2019.

Methodology: High-quality genomic DNA was extracted using a GenElute Bacterial Genomic DNA kit. The Nextera XT DNA Library Prep Kit was used for genomic library construction. Paired-end sequence reads were generated by an Illumina MiSeq instrument with the 600 cycles MiSeq

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Reagent Kit v3. Sequence data were assembled with A5-MiSeq pipeline software and the contigs were annotated by Rapid Annotation using Subsystems Technology (RAST).

Results: The obtained genome sequence of *Bacillus* AN2 included 21 contigs with a calculated size of 3,681,081 bp in length. The G + C content for the draft genome is 41.4%. A total of 3824 coding sequences (CDS) were predicted and encoded at least 88 tRNAs.

Keywords: Biofertilizers; biotechnology; inoculants; soil microbiota.

1. DATA DESCRIPTION

To reveal novel genes from *Bacillus* species, some bacterial strains were isolated by mixing 1 g of soil with 9 ml of NaCl 0.8% and incubating at 30°C for 1 h. The solution was decanted, and 1 ml of the supernatant was spread on MEMB agar plates [1,2] and incubated at 30°C for 4 days under aerobic conditions. One of the colonies recovered was named AN2, and its genome was sequenced. The genomic DNA was purified using a GenElute Bacterial Genomic DNA kit (Sigma-Aldrich, USA), and the library was constructed using a Nextera XT kit (Illumina). Paired-end sequence reads were generated by an Illumina MiSeq instrument with the 600 cycles MiSeq Reagent Kit v3. Reads were filtered for a Phred quality score of at least 20 and were assembled with A5-MiSeq pipeline software [3]. The contigs were annotated using the NCBI Prokaryotic Genomes Automatic Annotation Pipeline (PGAAP) and Rapid Annotation using Subsystems Technology (RAST) [4,5]. *Bacillus* species identification was achieved by using the JSpeciesWS server online with average nucleotide identity (ANIb) and MUMmer average nucleotide identity (ANIm) analysis [6,2]. The AN2 strain was identified as a member of the *Bacillus* group. The draft genome of *Bacillus* sp. AN2 consists of 3,681,081 bp distributed in 21 contigs, with an average GC content of 41.4%. The draft genome comprises 88 tRNAs. The bioinformatic analyses indicate that this strain carries many antimicrobial resistance genes and also most of the key genes associated with deconstructing plant cell walls [7,8] to improve the efficiency of processing biomass from agriculture residues by enzymatic hydrolyses such as cellulases, xylanases, and amylases have been identified.

2. CONCLUSION

The strain AN2 possesses numerous genes involved in deconstructing plant cell walls to improve the efficiency of processing biomass from agriculture residues by enzymatic hydrolyses such as cellulases, xylanases and

amylases. Many genes responsible for the bacterial strain resistance to several antibiotics and various toxic compounds were also identified. From this study, it can be deduced that the novel strain has a high capacity for biocontrol against soilborne pathogens and bioconversion of agro-industrial residues.

3. LIMITATIONS

Current data is based on the draft level genome such that the exact length of the genome, and the number of rRNA genes and repetitive elements, cannot be determined.

AVAILABILITY OF DATA

The data described in this Data Article can be freely and openly accessed on DDBJ/ENA/GenBank under the accession WUQP00000000. The version described in this paper is version WUQP01000000. It is important to share this data with other scientists as the data represent the first characterization of genome sequence data of a newly isolated *Bacillus* strain and it may hold a great promise to improve crop yield and biofuel industry. Link: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore/WUQP00000000>

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COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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